

Big Data, Data Science: What Real Usefulness for Business? "Innovation by the data"

Steve NKAM NKAM^a

^a*Paris, France*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Big data consists of the accumulation of a very large amount of data (much larger than the capacities of a personal computer), then the real-time analysis of this data. As for Data Science, it consists of developing algorithms using statistical methods or Machine Learning to solve specific problems. These techniques can rely on image analysis, text analysis, sensor correlation analysis, and much more. It is thus the design of algorithms using mathematical and statistical rules that characterizes Data Science. Big data, on the other hand, feeds very often on the algorithms of Data Science and allows them to be industrialized.

2. Aim

Big Data is above all a great opportunity for companies to innovate, develop their sales, their profits, their markets, to address new customers, and to create new offers. For customers of these companies and consumers, it is the assurance of a better customer experience in all their interactions with brands whether marketing, sales or customer service

3. Material and methods

Big data nowadays requires a lot of data storage and processing capabilities. To do this, storage levels of many materialized solutions (server, spark, Hadoop) and dematerialized (cloud) were set up, and level processing of numerous data processing applications (visualization, reporting, machine learning, etc.), such as our Pring Data Lab platform, and many more solutions to discover and extraordinary improvements in the making. To briefly explain why, today, only a tiny part of the data, often data customers or digital marketing, but also data from connected objects, various maintenance processes, statistics of use of products, vehicles, buildings, or even data collected as a result of natural, biological, etc. events ... are actually exploited by companies. The main reason for this state is that their collection, storage and exploitation have so far been very expensive. More expensive in fact than the apparent or immediate value generated by the exploitation of these data. Another reason comes from the fact that we did not know how to handle the gigantic data streams that are generated by the examples above. The Big Data approach makes it possible to collect, store,

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and analyze all this data at a much more reasonable cost than before thanks to new storage and especially analysis technologies. The consequence is that one can therefore consider analyzing and transforming into actionable information all those data that were once out of reach for both technical and financial reasons. The information density contained in these new data remains less compared, for example, with conventional transactional data. But this problem is somehow compensated by the huge volume of these data on the one hand, and especially by the possibility of cross-checking them via statistical algorithms.

4. Results

We are currently witnessing a turning point in history. Big Data technologies are transforming all industries and society as a whole. Some assume that Big Data is only a fad, but this phenomenon will revolutionize our world forever. Businesses collect, store and analyze vast amounts of data to improve their business, increase their revenue and optimize their services. Some firms go wrong, and make mistakes. However, many other companies use data analytics wisely. This is the case of Netflix, Uber, Google, Amazon, Dominos Pizza or Pring Data, just as an example. In all sectors, the uses of Big Data are flourishing and testify to the effectiveness of this new technology ...

5. Conclusions

Big Data is a heavy trend that is certainly neither fashionable nor blah-blah. This is not a fashion because in the field of usage, it corresponds to a need to work the data more deeply, more thoroughly, to create value, alongside technological capabilities that did not exist in the past. However, the technologies will continue to evolve and we can not yet speak of a real standard or standards in the field of Big data at the moment. Many uses of Big Data are in their infancy and we can expect to see the emergence of uses that we have not even thought of today. Big Data is a business turnaround at least as important as the Internet in the early 2000s. Companies that do not get started right now may find that in a few years by the competition. It is therefore better to start a small project quickly rather than wait until technologies and methods stabilize because then it will be too late.

6. Keywords

Big Data; Data Science; Enterprise; Pring Dat

Author biography

Steve NKAM NKAM CEO of Pring Data SAS